

A Study on Helping Attitude among Startups

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Abstract: Helping others is considered and sometimes expected to be a voluntary act. This behavior can be characterized as a helpful behavior that does not expect something in return. In general, the behavior of helping others would create a conducive environment especially when being instilled at an early stage of entrepreneurial journey. The study was conducted on 115 startup companies owners who participated under Tunas UsahawanBeliaBumiputera (TUBE 5.0) organized by SME Corporation, an agency under the Ministry of International Trade and Industries, Malaysia in early March 2018. The rate of return on the questionnaires was 48%. The objective is to find and compare the helping attitude of startups based on several demographic factors. The sample was selected through purposive sampling technique. The researchers used the Helping Attitude Scale (HAS) by Gary S. Nickell. It is a scale with 20-item to measure respondents' belief, feelings, and behaviors associated with helping others. The data was analyzed using Cross tabulation analysis. Based on the simple analyses, it is revealed that male startup owners possess better helping attitude than their female counterparts. Further analysis might give the researchers and the audience a better understanding and insights on this issue.

Keywords: Startups; Helping Attitude Scale; TUBE;

I. Introduction

Startups are parts of an economic ecosystem in any given country. In the past couple of years Malaysian startup ecosystem has incubated a great number of amazing startups that has attracted some of the top investors. The Malaysian startup scene is growing at a powerful speed according to 2016 statistics. Investments were up to US\$1.45 billion (MYR6.5 billion) in 2016, according to the Malaysia's Security Commission Annual Report 2016 (Pagan Research, 2018).

Helping others is a very important personal trait in which a person is concerned about the welfare of others. Entrepreneurs should be passionate about their ideas, goals and, of course, their companies. This passion is what drives them to do what they do. Some entrepreneurs love the adventure and excitement of creating something new, and once it is established they lose interest and move on to something else. Other entrepreneurs feel passionately about the product they are constructing or the sense of accomplishment they feel because they know they are helping other people, helping animals or helping the planet.

II. Defining Startups

According to Neil Blumenthal, co-founder and co-CEO of Warby Parker, "A startup is a company working to solve a problem where the solution is not obvious and success is not guaranteed" (Robehmed, 2018). According to the Indian Government, a startup can be defined as any business entity that has been incorporated 5 years or less, turnover for any of the financial years has not exceeded Rupees 25 crore, and is working towards innovation, development, deployment or commercialization of new products, processes or services driven by technology or intellectual property (Marg & Kunj, 2016). Startups are companies with a limited operating history. This company, in general has just been created, and is still in the development and market research phase. The term 'startup' has become popular internationally since the dot-com bubble when many internet-based companies have sprung up. Tech-startup is a startup that specializes in the high-tech industry. Startups can have various forms, but the term "startup company" is often associated with companies that are fast-growing and technology-oriented. Investors are attracted to new companies which are clearly

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characterized by their risk and scalability. So, this startup tends to have a lower 'bootstrapping cost', higher risk, and a higher potential for ROI-return on investment. Successful startups are usually more 'scalable' than established businesses, meaning startups have the potential to grow faster with limited capital, labor or land investment.

III. Background of Bumiputera Youth Entrepreneurs Program (TUBE)

The Bumiputera Youth Entrepreneurs Program or Tunas UsahawanBeliaBumiputera (TUBE) program is a government initiative to encourage the generation of youths to venture into business. It was launched during the Bumiputera Youth Entrepreneurs Congress organized by Ministry of International Trade and Industry of Malaysia (MITI) on 27-29 March 2014. During the Congress' closing ceremony on 29 March 2014, the Prime Minister announced an allocation of RM10 million to SME Corporation Malaysia (SME Corp) to implement the TUBE Program in 2014 (Bahagian Teknologi Maklumat, SME Corp. Malaysia, 2018). The program directly supports the nation's youth development policy where entrepreneurship is one of the key areas of focus for youth to move forward. SME Corp is committed to producing 12,000 young Bumiputera entrepreneurs through the TUBE Mega by 2020. Through the implementation of the TUBE Mega program, an estimated 37,000 new job opportunities could be created that could generate RM1.1 billion of accumulated sales value and contributed RM450 million to Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

The program targets Bumiputera youths between the ages of 18 and 30 who have deep interest in engaging in entrepreneurship, especially youths who have basic skills certificates from local training institutions or skills centers. The main objective of the TUBE Program is to 1) nurturing and cultivating entrepreneurial spirit among youths, 2) youth paradigm shift from job seeker to owner or business entrepreneur; and 3) forming resilience and identity among youth in managing their own businesses. This TUBE program is specially designed to prepare youth who want to start a business to have mental and physical resilience, as well as being exposed to the real world business landscape and challenges. This is done through three phases of implementation. In Phase 1, eligible participants will follow bootcamp-based military basic physical training to test the power of the mind, learn how to make strategic decisions, courage, leadership characterization and teamwork spirit. This is in preparation for the many challenges that will be faced while doing business. Selection of participants was strictly conducted via interview session to ensure only highly motivated participants will join the program.

Next, during the Phase 2, participants will be exposed to the latest business landscape; including information on the types of assistance and facilities provided by various ministries and agencies to start a business. Participants will also learn various business acquisitions including basic accounting, product marketing and services, as well as presentation ideas and business plans. Finally, in Phase 3 - Participants who passed Phase 1 and Phase 2 will carry out business based on the Business Plan presented to the current Panel of Assessors in Phase 2. The business development of participants in this phase will be guided and monitored through the Buddy System by the Business Counselor SME Corp. Malaysia. The 12-month coaching and monitoring period seeks to ensure TUBERs receive adequate advisory services, so that the business will continue to be resilient and sustainable. All successful participants will be eligible to apply a start-up business grant worth RM15,000.

Since 2014, 2,433 youths underwent training, with 99% of them or 2419 has registered new businesses. From these, SME Corp recorded a RM54.6mil in sales while creating 4,414 new jobs in the same period. In 2018, about 2,000 participants has joined the TUBE program executed at 15 different locations all over Malaysia. This program was jointly organized by government agencies, universities and industry partners (Utusan Borneo Online, 2018).

During the Phase 2, universities were responsible to conduct the training session. A special entrepreneurship and business management module was built to expose participants about this. USIM lecturers was assigned to handle TUBERs in Negeri Sembilan. About 115 participants had joined TUBE in Negeri Sembilan located at Ulu Pari PLKN Camp.

IV. Helping Attitudes Scale

According to Nickell (1998), helping attitude can be defined as the beliefs, feelings and behavior related to helping people. Helping Attitudes Scale (HAS) is a multidimensional attitude scale. It has been used to gauge the helping attitudes in many demographic layers. A study was conducted by Hafsah Jan to gauge the helping attitude of professional and non-professional college students in Kashmir, India. The study revealed that female possesses better helping attitude than male and also found that both professional and non-professional female college students have better helping attitudes than their male counterparts (Jan, 2017). Another study found that there is a significant

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correlation between helping attitude and purpose in life in older widowed women living with their families (Fernandes, Sanyal, & Fatima, 2015). In another research, it was concluded that helping attitude can be taught and learnt through exercises (Buragohain & Sonowal, 2016).

V. Methodology

The study was conducted on 115 startup companies owners who participated under Tunas UsahawanBeliaBumiputera (TUBE 5.0) organized by SME Corporation, an agency under the Ministry of International Trade and Industries, Malaysia in early March 2018. The rate of return on the questionnaires was 48%. The study is an exploratory study. The sample was selected through purposive sampling technique. The researchers used the Helping Attitude Scale (HAS) by Gary S. Nickell. It is a scale with 20-item to measure respondents' belief, feelings, and behaviors associated with helping others which includes 14 positive and 6 negative items. The range of scores on this scale extended from 20 to 100 with neutral score of 60 (Buragohain & Sonowal, 2016). The summation of all scores earned on all statements was taken as the total Helping Attitude score. Each item is answered on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

VI. Results

The mean for this Helping Attitude among Startup is 86.76 with a Standard Deviation of 8.604. The range of score is between 67 to100. The mean for Male is slightly higher than the Female at 89.03 compared to 84.04. It indicated that men has a more positive attitude towards helping. This is in contract with research done by Nickell, G. in 1998 (Nickell, 1998).

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha Result
Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.808	.851	20

Table 1 given above is the Reliability Statistics Table which provides the value for Cronbach alpha which in this case is .808 and reflects high reliability of the measuring instrument. Furthermore, it indicates high level of internal consistency with respect to the specific sample

Table 2: Gender Distribution of Respondents
Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	25	45.5	45.5	45.5
Male	30	54.5	54.5	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Chart 1: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Table 2 and Chart 1 given above illustrate the gender distribution of respondents which provides the gender percentage of the respondents. 54.55% of the respondents are male while 45.45% are female.

Table 3: Type of Business

		Type of Business			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Limited liability	2	3.6	3.6	3.6
	Partnership	3	5.5	5.5	9.1
	Sdn Bhd	3	5.5	5.5	14.5
	Sole proprietorship	47	85.5	85.5	100.0
	Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Chart 2: Type of Business

Table 3 and Chart 2 given above illustrate the type of business of respondents. In terms of forms of business, 3.64% are registered as limited liability company, 5.45% as partnership, 5.45% as Sendirian Berhad, and 85.45% are registered as sole proprietorship business.

Table 4: Type of Industry

		Industry			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agriculture	10	18.2	18.2	18.2
	Clothing	7	12.7	12.7	30.9
	Food	21	38.2	38.2	69.1
	Services	17	30.9	30.9	100.0
	Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Chart 3: Type of Industry

Table 4 and Chart 3 given above illustrate the type of industry of respondents. In terms of forms of business, 18.18% are in the agricultural industry, 12.73% are in the clothing industry, 38.18% are in the food industry, and 30.91% are in the services industry.

Table 5: Years in the Industry

		Involvement in business			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1 year	10	18.2	18.2	18.2
	2 year	2	3.6	3.6	21.8
	3 year	2	3.6	3.6	25.5
	4 years	2	3.6	3.6	29.1
	Just Started	22	40.0	40.0	69.1
	Less than 1 year	17	30.9	30.9	100.0
	Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Chart 4: Years in the Industry

Table 5 and Chart 4 given above illustrate years of involvement in business of the respondents. 40% of the have just started setting up their business, 30.91% less than 1 year, 18.18% 1 year, 3.64% 2 years, 3.64% 3 years and another 3.64% has been involved in business in 4 years.

Table 6: Numbers of Staff

Number of Staff (Not including the Owner)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1 employee	38	69.1	69.1	69.1
2 to 5 employees	17	30.9	30.9	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Chart 5: Numbers of Staff

Table 6 and Chart 5 given above illustrate numbers of staff in the business. 69.09% of the respondents have only 1 worker in their business while 30.91% have between 2 to 5 employees in their business.

Table 7: Gender * Amount Allocated for the Needy (2017) Crosstabulation

		Amount Allocated for the Needy (2017)			Total
		Below RM500	RM1001 to RM5000	RM500 to RM1000	
Gender	Female	20	1	4	25
	Male	17	2	11	30
Total		37	3	15	55

Table 7 illustrate the 2017 allocation for the needy based on gender. For female respondents, 80% allocated below RM500, 16% between RM500 to RM1000 and 4% allocated between RM1001 to RM5000 for the needy. For male respondents, 56.7% allocated below RM500, 36.7% between RM500 to RM1000 and 6.6% allocated between RM1001 to RM5000 for the needy.

Table 8: Helping others is usually a waste of time

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	1.0	43	78.2	78.2
	3.0	7	12.7	12.7
	4.0	1	1.8	1.8
	5.0	4	7.3	7.3
Total		55	100.0	100.0

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Based on Table 8, 78.2% of the respondents are strongly disagree that helping others is usually a waste of time. 17.7% are neither agree nor disagree that helping others is usually a waste of time. 7.3% strongly agree that helping others is usually a waste of time.

Table 9: When given the opportunity, I enjoy aiding others who are in need

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 3.0	3	5.5	5.5	5.5
4.0	10	18.2	18.2	23.6
5.0	42	76.4	76.4	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 9, 76.4% of the respondents enjoyed aiding others when given the opportunity to do so while 5.5% are neither agree nor disagree. 18.2% agreed that they enjoyed aiding others when given the opportunity

Table 10: If possible, I would return lost money to the rightful owner.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 3.0	2	3.6	3.6	3.6
4.0	12	21.8	21.8	25.5
5.0	41	74.5	74.5	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Based on Table 10, 74.5% of the respondents would return lost money to the rightful owner while 21.8% agreed to do so. 3.6% neither agree nor disagree that they would return the lost money to the rightful owner.

Table 11: Helping friends and family is one of the great joys in life.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 3.0	1	1.8	1.8	1.8
4.0	5	9.1	9.1	10.9
5.0	49	89.1	89.1	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Based on Table 11, 89.1% of the respondents felt strongly agree that helping friends and family is one of the great joy in life while 9.1% agreed to that statement. 1.8% neither agree nor disagree with that statement.

Table 12: I would avoid aiding someone in a medical emergency if I could

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid 1.0	31	56.4	56.4
2.0	9	16.4	16.4
3.0	6	10.9	10.9
4.0	3	5.5	5.5
5.0	6	10.9	10.9
Total	55	100.0	100.0

According to Table 12, 56.4% of the respondents felt strongly disagree that they would avoid aiding someone in medical emergency while 10.9% felt the opposite way. 16.4% of the respondents disagreed that they would avoid helping someone in medical emergency while 5.5% felt the opposite way. 10.9% neither agree nor disagree with this statement.

Table 13: It feels wonderful to assist others in need

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 4.0	13	23.6	23.6	23.6
5.0	42	76.4	76.4	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

From Table 13, 76.4% of the respondents felt strongly agree that they felt wonderful to assist others in need while 23.6% agreed to that statement.

Table 14: Volunteering to help someone is very rewarding

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2.0	2	3.6	3.6	3.6
3.0	4	7.3	7.3	10.9
4.0	8	14.5	14.5	25.5
5.0	41	74.5	74.5	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

It is shown in Table 14 that 74.5% of the respondents felt strongly agree that volunteering to help someone is very rewarding while 14.5% agreed to that statement. 7.3% neither agree nor disagree to that statement. 3.6% respondents disagree that volunteering to help someone is very rewarding.

Table 15: I dislike giving directions to stranger who are lost

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid 1.0	27	49.1	49.1
2.0	11	20.0	20.0
3.0	10	18.2	18.2
4.0	1	1.8	1.8
5.0	6	10.9	10.9
Total	55	100.0	100.0

Based on Table 15, 49.1% strongly disagree that they dislike giving directions to lost stranger, 20% disagree, 18.2% neither agree nor disagree, 1.8% agree while 10.9% strongly agree that they dislike giving directions to lost stranger.

Table 16: Doing volunteer work makes me feel happy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2.0	1	1.8	1.8	1.8
3.0	5	9.1	9.1	10.9
4.0	15	27.3	27.3	38.2
5.0	34	61.8	61.8	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

From Table 16, 61.8% of the respondents are strongly agree with the statement that doing volunteer works make them happy while 27.3% agreed with that statement. 9.1% are neither agree nor disagree. 1.8% felt disagree that doing volunteer work makes them happy.

Table 17: I donate time or money to charities every month

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	1	1.8	1.8	1.8
2.0	5	9.1	9.1	10.9
3.0	22	40.0	40.0	50.9
4.0	11	20.0	20.0	70.9
5.0	16	29.1	29.1	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 17, 29.1% strongly agree that they donate time or money to charities every month., 20% agree, 40% neither agree nor disagree, 9.1% disagree while 1.8% strongly disagree that they donate time or money to charities every month.

Table 18: Unless they are part of my family, helping the elderly isn't my responsibility

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	4	7.3	7.3	7.3
2.0	4	7.3	7.3	14.5
3.0	3	5.5	5.5	20.0
4.0	13	23.6	23.6	43.6
5.0	31	56.4	56.4	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

From Table 18, 56.4% strongly agree that they will not help the elderly unless they are part of the family, 23.6% agree, 5.5% neither agree nor disagree, 7.3% disagree while 7.3% strongly disagree that they will not help the elderly unless they are part of the family.

Table 19: Children should be thought about the importance of helping others

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	1	1.8	1.8	1.8
4.0	10	18.2	18.2	20.0
5.0	44	80.0	80.0	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Based on Table 19, 1.8% of the respondents strongly disagree that children should be thought about the importance of helping while 80% felt the other way. 18.2% neither agree nor disagree.

Table 20: I plan to donate my organs when I die with the hope that they will help someone else live.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	1	1.8	1.8	1.8
2.0	3	5.5	5.5	7.3
3.0	23	41.8	41.8	49.1
4.0	8	14.5	14.5	63.6
5.0	20	36.4	36.4	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

From Table 20, 36.4% strongly agree that they plan to donate my organs when they die with the hope that they will help someone else live, 14.5% agree, 41.8% neither agree nor disagree, 5.5% disagree while 1.8% strongly disagree that they plan to donate my organs when they die.

Table 21: I try to offer my help with any activities my community or school groups are carrying out.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2.0	2	3.6	3.6	3.6
3.0	6	10.9	10.9	14.5
4.0	20	36.4	36.4	50.9
5.0	27	49.1	49.1	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Table 21 shows that, 49.1% strongly agree that they try to offer their help with any activities in their community or school groups are carrying out, 36.4% agree, 10.9% neither agree nor disagree, while 3.6% disagree agree that they try to offer their help with any activities in their community or school groups are carrying out.

Table 22: I feel at peace with myself when I have helped others.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2.0	1	1.8	1.8	1.8
3.0	1	1.8	1.8	3.6
4.0	18	32.7	32.7	36.4
5.0	35	63.6	63.6	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Based on the Table 22 above, 63.6% strongly agree that they feel at peace with themselves when they have helped others, 32.7% agree, 1.8% neither agree nor disagree, while 1.8% disagree agree that they feel at peace with themselves when they have helped others.

Table 23: If the person in front of me in the check-out line at a store was a few cents short, I would pay the differences.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2.0	1	1.8	1.8	1.8
	3.0	5	9.1	9.1	10.9
	4.0	17	30.9	30.9	41.8
	5.0	32	58.2	58.2	100.0
	Total	55	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 23, 58.2% strongly agree that they feel at peace with themselves when they have helped others, 30.9% agree, 9.1% neither agree nor disagree, while 1.8% disagree agree that they feel at peace with themselves when they have helped others.

Table 24: I feel proud when I know that my generosity has benefited a needy person.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.0	1	1.8	1.8	1.8
	2.0	1	1.8	1.8	3.6
	3.0	1	1.8	1.8	5.5
	4.0	15	27.3	27.3	32.7
	5.0	37	67.3	67.3	100.0
	Total	55	100.0	100.0	

From Table 24, 67.3% strongly agree that they feel proud when they know that their generosity has benefited a needy person, 27.3% agree, 1.8% neither agree nor disagree, 1.8% disagree while 1.8% strongly disagree that they they feel proud when they know that their generosity has benefited a needy person.

Table 25: Helping people does more harm than good because they come to rely on others and not themselves.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	1.0	21	38.2	38.2
	2.0	10	18.2	18.2
	3.0	9	16.4	16.4
	4.0	8	14.5	14.5
	5.0	7	12.7	12.7
	Total	55	100.0	100.0

Based on Table 25, 12.7% strongly agree that helping people does more harm than good because they come to rely on others and not themselves, 14.5% agree, 16.4% neither agree nor disagree, 18.2% disagree while 38.2% strongly disagree that they helping people does more harm than good because they come to rely on others and not themselves.

Table 26: Giving aid to the poor is the right thing to do.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 3.0	2	3.6	3.6	3.6
4.0	18	32.7	32.7	36.4
5.0	35	63.6	63.6	100.0
Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Finally, Table 26 shows that 63.6% of the respondents felt strongly agree that giving aid to the poor is the right thing to do while 32.7% agreed to that statement. 3.6% neither agree nor disagree with that statement.

VII. Discussions and Conclusions

Even previous research as mentioned earlier showed that women have the tendency to help others more than men, specifically for this study, it was revealed that the opposite was true. From this study, it is also found that the allocation of fund for the needy is higher for men compared to women. The result could be further refined if the response rate is higher than 48%. Another interesting finding was that most of the respondents have only started their business 1 year or less. This might be another contributing factor. One might argue that they need money to help people and the first few years of establishment is where the money is needed the most. In conclusion, encouraging startups to help people especially in their foundation years can create a strong inner voluntary trait. Helping others is a very important personal trait in which a person is concerned about the welfare of others. Entrepreneurs should be passionate about their ideas, goals and, of course, their companies. Further analysis might give the researchers and the audience a better understanding and insights on this issue.

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